

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF CERTAIN ACE INHIBITORS, SITOTEC, OMEPRAZOLE AND THEIR COMBINATIONS ON THE PROCESSES OF POL AND NO FORMATION IN THE GASTRIC MUCOSA IN INDOMETHACIN GASTROPATHY

Yakubov A. B.
Pulatova D. B.
Musayeva L. J.
Ilkhomova Z. E.

Tashkent Medical Academy
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960299>

Abstract: In the pathogenesis of NSAID gastropathy, the state of lipid peroxidation (POL) in the gastric mucosa is of great importance. Recently, there has been evidence that ACE inhibitors have a corrective effect on the processes of SEX and NO formation in various organs. This circumstance served as the basis for studying the effectiveness of some ACEinhibitors in indomethacin-induced gastropathy in animals

Key words: i-ACE, omeprazole, sitotec, oxidative stress, nitric oxide, stomach.

Introduction. The ideas about the etiology and pathogenesis of stomach aches over a long historical period have been inextricably linked with the discussion of the role of the infectious factor. The wide prevalence of Helicobacter pylori (HP) - associated diseases of the gastroduodenal zone, which has no tendency to decrease, the recurrent nature of the infection, and treatment difficulties associated with the short duration of eradication of the pathogen make it relevant to study the mechanisms capable of maintaining the persistent nature of the inflammatory process. The problem of helicobacteriosis remains one of the central problems in modern clinical gastroenterology. Thus, in countries with a high socio-economic level, the prevalence of Helicobacter pylori (HP) infection is 4-25%, with a low one - 60-90% or more. Treatment of Helicobacter pylori (Hp)-associated diseases (chronic gastritis type B, Hp-positive peptic ulcer, cancer and gastric maltoma) is becoming less effective every year. The main reason is the annually growing secondary resistance of Hp to antibacterial agents included in their eradication schemes. The ineffectiveness of Hp eradication therapy has become an increasing problem in everyday medical practice. Inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract caused by Helicobacter pylori can lead to its dysfunction, which can contribute to the development of high blood pressure.

The purpose of our study is a comparative study of the effect of certain ACE inhibitors, sitotec, omeprazole and their combinations on the processes of POL and NO formation in the gastric mucosa in indomethacin gastropathy in animals with experimental rheumatoid arthritis.

Materials and methods of research. Experimental studies were carried out on 78 male rats of a mixed population weighing 160-200 g, which were on a regular vivarium diet. The animals were divided into 13 groups of 6 individuals each.

Results. Indomethacin significantly accelerates the processes of oxidative stress. In animals of this group, the content of POL, MDA and CHL products was 130.4 and 179.0% higher than the control values, respectively. Catalase activity decreased by more than 2.5 times, and SOD by more than 2 times. Ace inhibitors, omeprazole and sitotec have an antioxidant effect on the gastric mucosa. In animals with enalapril, compared with the indicators of the GERA+H₂O group, the content of MDA decreased by 38.5%, and CL by 47.7%. Catalase activity increased by 79.0%, SOD by 42.8%

Conclusions. One of the causes of indomethacin damage to the stomach is an increase in the processes of oxidative stress and a decrease in the content of the substrate and the activity of NO formation enzymes.

References:

1. Akhmedov M. A., Shamsiev A.M. Acute dilation of the stomach in a 13-year-old child //Vestnik khirurgii imeni II Grekova. – 1970. – Vol. 105. – No. 12. – p. 82.
2. Ushkalova E.A., Ushkalova A.V. Pharmacoeconomical consequences of complications of drug therapy // Clinical trials of medicines in Russia. - 2003. - No.3-4. - pp. 34-41.
3. Metelitsa V.I. Handbook of clinical pharmacology of cardiovascular medicines. - M.: Publishing House Binom - St. Petersburg.: Publishing House Nevsky Dialect, 2002. - 926 p
4. Kukes V.G., Starodubtsev A.K. Clinical pharmacology and pharmacotherapy. - M.: GEOTAR-MED, 2003. - 640 p.

